

Measurement cell for *in situ* elemental mapping of (photo-) catalytically active substances in wet soft matter samples by micro X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy

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Abstract

To meet the demand for analyzing the spatial distribution of elements in native soft matter materials for (light-driven) catalysis using two-dimensional micro X-ray fluorescence, a measurement cell and clamping tool setup was developed. The cell features a large measurement area, isolates the sample to prevent evaporation, provides structural support and can be easily assembled. For the first time, this setup enables the measurement of moist samples of functionalized soft matter materials without additional preparation over prolonged periods without falsification of the measurements due to changes during the measurement. This development enables

semi-quantitative comparisons of the elemental composition and distribution of different samples, as well as within the same sample, over time. The applicability and reproducibility of the measurement cell is demonstrated for so-called POMbranes, nanoporous block copolymer membranes functionalized with the polyoxometalate cluster $[\text{Co}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{PW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2]^{10-}$, which could be measured under wet conditions. For these samples, the improved homogeneity of the elemental distribution with increased loading time was proven quantitatively. The improved measurement conditions enable identification of small variations that occurred accidentally during the experiments.

1. Introduction

Artificial photocatalytic systems play a crucial role in solar energy conversion, as they enable light-driven productive chemistry such as water splitting or CO₂ reduction. This opens promising pathways towards renewable energy technologies while reducing dependence on fossil fuels. [1–3] Recent research has shown that integration of catalytically active components, *i.e.*, light absorber/photosensitizer and catalyst into soft matter environments is beneficial to control the overall activity and efficiency of light harvesting. Immobilization of catalytically active components is also a potent strategy towards coupling of reductive and oxidative half-reactions. Membranes that link compartments for the two half-reactions are key components for coupling half-reactions. These membranes cannot only be used to control mass transport between the compartments but also serve catalytic functions. One example of a such photocatalytic system are so-called “POMbranes”, self-supporting nanoporous membranes where catalysts (CAT) and photosensitizers (PS) can be electrostatically or covalently immobilized to enable subsequent light-driven hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) or water oxidation catalysis (WOC).[4,5] In these materials, polyoxometalate-water oxidation catalysts (POM-WOCs) are embedded in functional soft matter matrices together with light absorbers (photosensitizers) to enable light-driven WOC. Unlike conventional homogenous systems, POMbranes provide a unique platform for catalyst functionalization, reuse and long-term stability while maintaining its catalytic performance. These membranes are made of polystyrene-*block*-poly(2-(dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate) (PS-*b*-PDMAEMA) and are functionalized with the POM-WOC [Co₄(H₂O)₂(PW₉O₃₄)₂]¹⁰⁻ and a photosensitizer, e.g. [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺. [1,6,7] The quality of the functionalization is a key property for the water oxidation activity and thus, thorough characterization of the POMbrane is crucial for the development and synthesis of highly active materials and systems for artificial photosynthesis. Particularly, this includes laterally resolved quantity, stability, and homogeneity of the functional entities present in the membrane in addition to information on the overall composition and macroscopic catalytic efficiency of the systems.

Two-dimensional micro X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (2D μ XRF) is a versatile, non-destructive imaging technique for multi-elemental analysis. In benchtop instruments, 2D μ XRF enables the acquisition of elemental distribution maps for elements with an atomic number above 11 with a resolution of a few micrometers by focusing an incoming X-ray beam onto a sample positioned on a movable stage. [8] Common application fields of laboratory-based 2D μ XRF include materials science [9], geology [10], archaeology [11], and forensics. [8] The investigation of soft matter materials by μ XRF is less common, however there are some examples showing that elemental mapping in thin section of biological tissues [12] or gels [13] is feasible. Soft materials primarily consist of organic macromolecules and water and are therefore dominated by elements with low atomic numbers, such as carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen. These light elements exhibit low X-ray absorption and fluorescence yields and are therefore often referred to as “dark matter” materials in XRF analysis. Consequently, the analysis of thin homogeneous layers of soft materials provides lateral distribution maps of minor and trace elements. However, samples are typically dried before μ XRF examination, since the removal of water significantly reduces X-ray scattering and thereby enhances detection sensitivity. However, drying can be challenging for samples prone to

deformation, as it may cause warping or other undesired structural changes. This issue is particularly pronounced for porous membranes, which tend to shrink, curl, or become brittle upon drying. Such changes are often irreversible, rendering subsequent analyses of the same sample unfeasible. Complex and time-consuming sample preparation *e.g.*, embedding or freeze drying, is then performed to preserve their original properties. [14] *In situ* measurement of the materials in their original form would be highly preferable providing accurate representation of native conditions. The possibility of μ XRF measurements being conducted under ambient air conditions enables in principle the direct investigation of moist samples. [15] For laboratory-based μ XRF, examples of such measurements include the investigation of plants under *in vivo* conditions. For this purpose, a well-defined sample preparation in dedicated measurement setups is essential to ensure reproducible results. Such a sample holder should maintain sample integrity, minimize solvent evaporation and sample movement, prevent change or bending of the sample and thus improve reproducibility of the measurement. Plant samples can be placed between thin X-ray transparent foil in a sandwich-type fashion and then fixed with a plastic frame to avoid evaporation of water.[16–18] *Fittschen et al.* [19] used a 3D printed sample holder for the analysis of plant leaves and *Mijovilovich et al.* [20] performed their μ XRF measurements of plants in a custom-made sample cell that maintains a constant humidity level. The cell was made out of acrylic glass (PMMA) and had a window made from an 80 μ m thick printer foil as well as in- and outlets for the air and nutrient media. [20–22] Another example for a cell designed for confocal μ XRF measurements at the liquid/solid interface to study of the corrosion process of steel in artificial seawater was developed by *Hirano et al.* [23]. The cell, fabricated from polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), features a screw-type lid and a polyimide-film window. In a similar set-up, *Tsuji et al.* [24] performed confocal μ XRF measurements at the solid/liquid interface of an iron plate in a CuSO_4 solution.

Although several custom-designed sample cells have been described in the literature, these designs are not suitable for the samples investigated in this work, as the specimens must remain both planar and hydrated throughout the entire measurement. Any changes in thickness and/or water content may lead to biased or falsified interpretation of the obtained data. [25] Foil-sandwich cells reported for *in vivo* plant studies perform well because the internal structure of plant tissue provides mechanical stability. However, this characteristic is not shared by many other materials. Furthermore, in plant samples, the water is contained within the tissue itself, whereas in applications involving the above-mentioned catalytically active membranes, the water is not only within the membrane pores but additionally surrounds the sample. Accordingly, an appropriate sample cell must ensure sufficient sealing and provide structural support while maintaining the sample's integrity, avoiding excessive pressure or mechanical strain. This necessitates a stable, well-sealed measurement chamber that prevents any mechanical stress or damage to the sample. Therefore, in this work a cell for 2D μ XRF analysis of moist, deformable soft matter materials, such as active membranes for light-driven catalysis is developed. The cell design enables the controlled and reproducible *in situ* investigation of elemental distributions in native, hydrated POMbranes under well-defined conditions.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Drying experiment covered vs uncovered membrane

As a reference case, the impact of undesired sample drying on the element mapping and the quality and reproducibility of the data was studied first. To this end, native wet POM-functionalized block copolymer membranes were examined over 2 hours using μ XRF element mapping of the POM catalyst elements W and Co. In Figure 1, W distribution of uncovered sample is compared to a sample that is covered by a thin X-ray transparent foil, *i.e.*, placed in a foil-sandwich. (see SI, Figures S2, S3 and S4 for additional images, the corresponding Co K_{α} element maps and the corresponding W L_{α} intensity histograms).

Figure 1: POMbrane samples over time starting from native, wet sample ($t_{\text{start}}=0$ min) for a sample in a foil sandwich (foil-covered, left) and placed openly on a foil (uncovered, right). a) Photographic images; b) Corresponding W L_{α} (8.4 keV) distribution maps; c,d) Corresponding line scans indicated by dashed lines in Figure b) for covered sample starting at $t_{\text{start}} = 0$ min (blue) and after 120 min (rose) and for uncovered sample at $t_{\text{start}} = 0$ min and after 15 min (orange).

The change in color of the membranes from dark orange (wet samples) to light yellow clearly shows the progressing evaporation of water with time. The overall measurement duration for recording an entire μ XRF element map in this measurement (area of 5.5x5.5 mm²; dwell time of 10 ms per pixel) is around 15 min. The uncovered membrane dries rapidly within this time and the second mapping ($t_{\text{start}}=15$ min) is

performed on the dry sample, while the covered sample shows first dry areas only after 120 min and is completely dry after 240 min. The corresponding $W K_{\alpha}$ maps in Figure 1b) show intensity changes over time that are a result of two effects. First, the dried regions exhibit higher apparent intensities, as reduced X-ray scattering by water lowers the background signal. Second, drying induces sample deformation; *i.e.*, regions that warp and incline toward the detector are detected with increased sensitivity, further amplifying their apparent signal intensity. The latter becomes obvious when comparing the line scans of wet and dried membrane in Figure 1c, d). These artifacts make sample comparison and reliable quantification difficult or even impossible. Covering the sample with a thin X-ray-transparent foil minimizes these effects by slowing down the unwanted drying process and ensuring stable conditions during the measurement time and up to 120 min, which is visible in the constant intensity in the line scans in Figure 1c).

In the next step, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of $Co K_{\alpha}$ and $W L_{\alpha}$ were determined from the sum spectra of the respective element maps (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). Constant SNR over time is desirable to allow reliable comparison between data sets and to improve semi-quantitative interpretation of spectra.

Figure 2: Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of $Co K_{\alpha}$ (bottom) and $W L_{\alpha}$ (top) for uncovered (diamonds) and covered (triangle) membrane sample.

While, for the covered sample SNR remains nearly constant for up to about 120 min, followed by an increase after 150 min, in uncovered samples a strong increase in SNR within the first 15 min occurs and then stabilizes at a higher value because of the absence of water which reduces scattering and absorption effects.

These results clearly demonstrate that covering of native, wet POMbranes is essential for achieving reproducible measurements. This is particularly important for spectra interpretation for the semi-quantitative comparison of different membranes or at distinct time points (*e.g.*, before and after catalysis). However, the foil-sandwich configuration used in the above experiments is unsuitable as a routine measurement setup, as its

practical handling is cumbersome and lacks reproducibility. Mounting the sample onto the thin support film requires repeatedly screwing and unscrewing the upper frame, and manually attaching the upper foil to a smooth surface is both challenging and difficult to reproduce reliably.

2.2. Measurement cell and clamping tool setup

For better sample handling and controllable reproducible measurements, a measurement setup consisting of the measurement cell, a two-parted frame, shown in Figure 3a) and b), and a clamping tool, Figure 3c), were developed. The wet sample is placed in the measurement cell base and the frame ensures that the Ultralene® film stays in place. To be compatible with the μ XRF technique, all main components were made from light elements, *i.e.*, avoiding the use of metal parts. The components were designed to meet the following requirements: i) expose a large measurement area to reduce signal interference, ii) create an isolated space that contains the wet sample and retains water during the measurement, and iii) allow for easy and reproducible assembly.

To ensure reproducible assembly of the measurement cell, a clamping tool for the application of an Ultralene® film to the measurement cell was developed. The design target was to reduce the previously mentioned effects through even film tension on top of the sample, keeping the sample planar and the water film distribution uniform. Furthermore, the tool should allow reuse of the Ultralene® film between samples.

Figure 3: a) Exploded view of μ XRF-compatible measurement cell. b) Fully assembled measurement cell. c) Clamping tool model developed for even measurement film application.

Due to the reduced number of separate components, the developed setup allows for significantly easier sample handling and assembly, reducing the risk of mechanical manipulation to the sample. Figure 4 shows that the film can be applied evenly using the clamping tool and allows a single person to fully assemble the cell without assistance for easier day-to-day use. The main observable trade-off is an overall poorer SNR due to an increased material thickness underneath the sample. The influence of the cell base material and thickness is shown in the Supporting Information (see SI, Figure S5). However, the characterization results on film application and ease of cell assembly for wet samples demonstrate that the developed measurement cell together with the clamping tool ensure reproducibility and precision of μ XRF measurements, which is prioritized in this work. This is demonstrated using Cu standard samples.

Figure 4: Photo of stretched Ultralene[®] foil a) on bottom shell b) and with top shell.

2.3. Reproducibility tests

Reproducibility tests were performed with cellulose nitrate membranes as simulated samples. The membranes were soaked in aqueous Cu standard solution before inserting the wet samples into the cell. The effect of water distribution and potential unwanted drying on the signal was evaluated, as well as the handling and reproducibility of sample insertion into the new measurement cell. First, the reproducibility of introducing the sample into the cell was visually verified (see SI, Figure S6ab). Then, the Cu SNR of the ten individual membranes loaded sequentially into the cell were determined by recording the μ XRF spectra (see SI, Figure S7) of each entire sample immediately after the cell was placed in the instrument ($t_{\text{start}} = 0$ min) and after 15 min (Exemplary Cu maps are presented in SI, Figure S6c).

Figure 5: Reproducibility tests using 10 different membrane samples (individual sample indicated by color) soaked in Cu solution, each measured twice at 0 min and 15 min directly after the first measurement: SNR of Cu K α . (One outlier was excluded from the data based on the *Grubbs* test at a confidence level of 95%.)

The results are shown in Figure 5 and demonstrate high reproducibility, as the relative standard deviation of the SNR is as low as 8%. The observed variations reflect the cumulative contributions of sample-to-sample differences, manual handling steps (including dipping the membrane into the solution and removing excess liquid), assembly and disassembly of the cell, and measurement variability. Since the differences between individual samples are more pronounced than those between consecutive measurements taken after 15 min, it can be concluded that the developed measurement cell enables highly reproducible μ XRF mapping of wet samples.

2.4. Application to real sample (loading experiment)

The applicability of the measurement cell with a real sample was evaluated with an unloaded block copolymer membrane sample, for which the loading behavior of the membrane was examined after different periods. For the use as catalytically active component, the membranes were loaded with active substances, e.g., photosensitizers and/or catalyst, prior to the catalytic experiments. This loading normally takes place in a flask, with or without stirring, for 24 hours. To realize a more homogeneous and reproducible loading, a flow-through membrane cell (referred to as “loading cell”, see SI, Figure S8) was used for loading in this work. The membranes

were inserted in this cell and a solution containing the catalyst (here: polyoxometalate cluster $[\text{Co}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{PW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2]^{10-}$) to be loaded onto the membrane was pumped through the loading cell for up to 24 hours. After this loading step, the respective membrane was transferred into the newly developed measurement cell and examined by μXRF with regard to the intensity and the homogeneity of the loaded catalyst elements. In Figure 6a, the Co K_α and W L_α μXRF maps are displayed. Comparing the intensities of the element maps already visually indicates an increase of catalyst loading with time. It can also be observed that the intensity distribution becomes more homogeneous for prolonged loading times.

Figure 6: a) Elemental distribution of Co K_α (6.9 keV) and W L_α (8.4 keV) after 1, 8, 16, and 24 h of loading experiment. Dashed line indicates position of line scans. b) Corresponding line scans (width 20 pixel) for Co K_α (left) and W L_α (right) of loading experiments over time (darker shade of color corresponds to increase in loading time). c) Intensity histograms of loading experiments over time for Co K_α and W L_α . Shaded area represents the range selected for peak analysis.

The line scans of Co K_α and W L_α (Figure 6b) show an increase in signal intensities over time. After approximately 8 h only minor changes in the measured intensities can be observed, suggesting that the loading capacity is reached. The intensity histograms (Figure 6c) reveal a consistent shift toward higher intensities with increasing loading

time. Most pronounced shift is observed between 1 h and 8 h, while only minimal changes occur beyond 8 h. Homogeneity of the loading was evaluated based on the full width at half maximum (FWHM) and the peak height of the histograms (see Table 1).

Table 1: Results of peak analysis of intensity histograms in Figure 6c).

	Peak Area	FWHM	Peak height
Tungsten (relative intensities 25 -120)			
1 h	155738	18.9	7693
8 h	154669	24.1	6208
16 h	150045	23.7	5928
24 h	152894	20.9	6733
Cobalt (relative intensities 10 - 35)			
1 h	-	-	-
8 h	149888	11.1	13164
16 h	146805	10.8	13006
24 h	148597	10.6	13620

The FWHM was found to decrease with time, while the peak height increased over time. These trends indicate a more homogeneous elemental distribution after 24 h compared to samples with shorter loading times. However, the changes observed beyond 8 h are small, implying that shorter loading times are sufficient to achieve a similarly homogeneous loading. These measurements also prove that the loading cell is well suited for homogeneously loading the membranes. A detailed inspection of the element maps also reveals details about the loading process and the conditions in the loading cell itself. After 16 hours a ring structure appears on the left side of the membrane, indicating a less homogenous distribution of Co and W in this region. This is a result of the installation of the membrane in the loading cell, which is sealed with an O-ring. For these measurements the O-ring accidentally shifted onto the membrane, which disturbed the flow through the membrane in these regions during loading, eventually causing a higher catalyst loading. After additional 8 hours of loading, this is not visible anymore, which indicates a compensation of the maldistribution with time. This example clearly underlines the potential of μ XRF measurements with the developed measurement cell to characterize the elemental distribution in wet 2D materials. With this measurement cell at hand, it becomes possible to link spatial elemental distributions to catalytic activity.

3. Conclusion

In this work, the limitations for measuring elemental distributions of native soft matter materials with two-dimensional micro X-ray fluorescence analysis were addressed by developing a novel measurement cell along with a clamping tool setup. The cell provides a large measurement area with a diameter of 2.5 cm, isolates the sample to avoid evaporation, provides structural support to the sample, and can be assembled easily and reproducibly. This allows for the first time to measure moist soft samples without additional sample preparation over prolonged periods without falsification of the measurements due to changes during the measurement. This approach enables, for the first time, a semi-quantitative comparison of elemental composition and distribution of different samples, as well as within the same sample at different stages, for example before and after catalysis.

Tests proved that variations induced by sample handling are below variations between different samples, demonstrating high reproducibility that can be realized with the developed measurement cell and clamping tool. The practical applicability was demonstrated for so-called POMbranes, nanoporous block copolymer membranes functionalized with the polyoxometalate cluster $[\text{Co}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{PW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2]^{10-}$, which could be measured under wet conditions. For these samples, the improved homogeneity of the elemental distribution with increased loading time could be proven quantitatively. The improved measurement conditions even enable the identification of small variations that accidentally occurred during the experiments.

Knowledge of the spatial distribution of catalytically active components is key for linking the macroscopically observed activity to the chemical and morphological properties of catalytically active materials. This is even more important for materials for light-driven catalysis since conclusions on the performance of a material have to consider spatially varying irradiation fields. In combination with heterogeneous distributions of active materials a meaningful interpretation of the results is only possible with a sound knowledge of this distribution. The presented measurement cell together with the clamping tool provides a solution to this demand, which will be extended in the future to enable also the measurement of elemental distributions during e.g., loading of membranes with catalysts or even during catalysis to study leaching.

4. Experimental

4.1. μ XRF measurements

For μ XRF measurements, M4 Tornado (Bruker Nano GmbH in Berlin, Germany) spectrometer is used. The instrument is equipped with Rh X-ray tube and is operated at maximum power (50 kV, 600 μ A). The polychromatic beam is focused to a spot size of around 25 μ m diameter by polycapillary lenses. The resulting X-ray fluorescence is detected by an XFlash 430 PA detector with an active area of 30 mm² and a resolution of <145 eV at Mn K α . Measurements were carried out under ambient air conditions, and no filters were applied. For elemental mappings, the normal scanning mode (from left to right, from top to bottom) and a dwell time of 10 ms per pixel were used.

4.2. Sandwich cell

For the experiments with covered and uncovered membrane samples, a modified version of the self-developed 3D-printed sample holder further described in *Müller et al.* [25] made of polylactide (PLA) was used (for details see SI, Figure S1). This consists of a lower part with a rectangular frame cut-out and a separate upper frame. A polyvinyl chloride (PVC) film (0.1 mm) serves as sample support onto which the wet membrane is placed. For optional sample covering, a thin (4 μ m) Ultralene[®] foil (Cole-Parmer SamplePrep, Metuchen NJ, USA) is attached to the upper frame. The POMbrane samples were taken out of the ultrapure water (UPW) storage solution, excess liquid was carefully removed before placing the membrane onto the PVC foil.

4.3. Design of measurement cell

The developed measurement cell was manufactured by the Ulm University workshop, using transparent polycarbonate (PC) for the top shell, black polyvinyl chloride (PVC) for the bottom shell, and polyethylene (PE) for the cell base, and connected by an M16 thread. The shell holds the film using an NBR O-ring and four M6 PE screws. The outer dimensions are identical to the first version, hence the platform and clamping tool remained unchanged. The base has two ports with UNF 1/4"-28 threads.

4.4. Cu loaded membrane filters

For reproducibility tests of the developed measurement cell a simulated sample was used and the sample insertion was repeated 10 times. Therefore, 10 membrane cellulose nitrate filters (0.45 μ m) (Hahnemühle FineArt GmbH, Dassel, Germany) were first soaked in 1000 mg L⁻¹ Cu standard solution in 0.5 M HNO₃ (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). The filter was removed from the solution, excess liquid was stripped off, and then the sample was placed into the cell. The μ XRF measurements were performed immediately after inserting the sample and after 15 minutes. The second measurement was started immediately after the first measurement, which took approximately 15 minutes. Each time a new membrane filter and a new cover foil were used.

4.5. Membrane fabrication and POM synthesis

For membrane preparation, the block copolymer is prepared following the synthesis by *Kund et al.* [1] Membranes were then fabricated as reported by *Schacher et al.* [26]

The $[\text{Co}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{PW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2]^{10-}$ polyoxometalate (POM) catalyst was prepared according to the procedure by Hill and co-workers. [27]

4.6. Membrane functionalization/loading in reactor setup

For membrane functionalization, a 0.64 mmol L^{-1} solution of the POM cluster $\text{Na}_{10}[\text{Co}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{PW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2] \times 27 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared according to *Kund et al.* [1]

The membranes were functionalized inside an SLA 3D-printed (Clear Resin V5, Formlabs GmbH, Berlin, Germany) membrane loading cell, consisting of a bottom distributor, a top cover, a silicone O-ring, mesh, and aluminum scaffolding with six M3x40 screws, with respective washers and bolts. The cell was connected to a fluid circuit *via* UNF 1/4"-28 threads cut into the distributor and cover. The fluid circuit included a glass reservoir with two GL14 threads, which contained the functionalization solution, and a KNF SIMDOS®10 FEM 1.10 TT.18 RC-P membrane pump to circulate the solution at 10 mL min^{-1} . All components were connected using 1/8" OD 1/16" ID FEP capillaries, attached to the reservoir *via* BOLA GL14 HT laboratory screw joints and IDEX PEEK flangeless 1/4-28 UNF flat bottom fittings to the cell and pump.

Further information on the membrane loading setup and parameters for loading can be found in the Supporting Information.

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